

The origin of particles and the expansion of space time.

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Abstract

This paper shows that you can create all particles from electrons, positrons and neutrinos in a simple and predictable manner. This paper posits the existence of an electro-magnetic structure; the *Maxwell Spin Cup* that gives rise to what appears to be quantised charge. The *Maxwell Spin Cup* consists of two rotating magnetic potentials. The magnetic potentials themselves are displaced forwards and backwards in time from the current time plane. A pair of temporally displaced dipoles is termed a *Sinclair Pair*. The rotating magnetic fields maintain a raised electric potential in the vicinity's of the pair. The paper postulates a time displacement force (a *time like force*) that draws the regions of forward displaced time and backwards displaced time together. The spin of the pair balances the centripetal *time like force*. The act of creating a Maxwell Spin Cup expands space time along the time like axis.

A neutrino is then two regions of time displaced space (where the dipoles of the Sinclair Pair have opposite sense) rotating around each other. The paper sets out the model of the *Maxwell Spin Cup* and proposes a mechanism by which they can be created from high energy photons. There are 8 possible configurations of the simplest *Maxwell Spin Cup* and they correspond to: spin-up-electrons, spin-down-electron, spin-up-positrons, spin-down-positrons and 4 neutrinos.

Cooper pairs are formed via quadrupole attraction between pairs of electrons with opposite spin.

Maxwell Spin Cups can be linked together to form compound particles like *pions*, *protons* and *neutrons* if time displaced dipoles are shared between two or three Maxwell Spin cups. The Heisenberg strut is proposed as the means by which the spin cups in compound particles are held apart and the mechanism of its creation accounts for expansion of space-time. The origin of mass is then the energy stored in the Heisenberg struts between the dipoles in linked Maxwell Spin Cups.

The paper makes a testable prediction that the structure of the neutron is [positron - electron - neutrino] and that there are two types of proton [positron - electron - positron] and [positron - neutrino - neutrino]. This paper predicts that neutron beta decay involves dipole flipping mediated by a passing neutrino. This paper predicts that hydrogen is created in stars as they expand space time in their growth phase.

Keywords: *origin of spin 1/2 particles, origin of quantisation of charge in particles, neutrino spin 1/2 temporal shift*

1 Introduction

Electrons (and positrons) have a series of documented properties:

- quantised charge [7].

- spin of +/- 1/2 [2].
- magnetic dipole moment [9, 8].
- electric dipole moment [11]
- rest mass [4].

Prior to this paper no satisfactory explanation has been given for why particle charge is quantised, what exactly gives rise to a spin 1/2 particle or why an electron should have a magnetic dipole moment or indeed an electric dipole moment. No explanation exists of the process by which a high energy gamma ray photon creates an electron/positron pair at a scattering event or any plausible explanation of what a neutrino is or what it is for.

This paper proposes a stable electro-magnetic structure that we term a *Maxwell Spin Cup* that maintains a region of raised electric potential. It also proposes a mechanism by which such a structure can be created by temporal drag in a scattering event.

The creation process naturally gives rise to a pair of oppositely charged *Maxwell Spin Cups*. Consideration of the creation process and the mysterious nature of spin 1/2 particles leads to the conclusion that it is possible to displace regions of space time *in* time. The displacement in time of a pair of regions, one forwards and one backwards seems to create a force between the regions. A pair of temporally displaced regions rotating about each other will have intrinsic angular momentum, it is likely that if the dipoles regions are aligned N-SN-S and S-NS-N then you have a neutrino (figure 2.2.1). We call a pair of temporally displaced rotating regions with dipoles in them a *Sinclair Pair*. It is possible that dark matter includes clouds of neutrinos shed from subatomic processes in stars. Section 2.2.1 postulates that the creation of the small temporal shift in the *Sinclair Pairs* acts to expand the time dimension of space time and gives a sense to the arrow of time. The build up of neutrinos over time will cause gravity to appear to change over time (the time axis of space time is stretch by neutrino creation).

In this model multi-quark particles are created by temporal cross linking of spatially distinct dipoles into multiple Maxwell Spin Cups. The mass in a compound particle then corresponds to the energy stored in the time like bonds between time entangled spin cups. The new kind of bond proposed here we call a Heisenberg strut (section 3.0.2) and the author postulates that the creation of Heisenberg struts forces an expansion in space time.

This paper is laid out as follows, section 2 illustrates the structure of a *Maxwell Spin Cup* and shows the 8 different configurations that correspond to spin-up-electrons, spin-down-electrons, spin-up-positrons and spin-down-positrons and some neutrinos. The differing magnetic quadrupole moments of the spin-up and spin-down versions account for the existence of Cooper-pairs. Apparent quantisation of charge results from there being one stable set of values for angular momentum, temporal displacement and spatial displacement in the *Sinclair Pair*. The author speculates that some component of cosmic background radiation results from photon emission as the electric and magnetic fields in the Maxwell spin cup settle into equilibrium as an electron or positron are formed.

Section 2.2.1 gives the proposed structure of a neutrino showing how a near mass less particle can have spin like properties.

Section 2.1 illustrates how a differential time like drag on a photon can distort it sufficiently to create a pair of *Maxwell Spin Cups*.

Section 3 shows how Maxwell Spin Cups can be compounded into heavy particles through time like cross linking of dipoles in multiple spin cups. The energy in the time like bounds (the *Heisenberg strut*) is the origin of mass in compound particles. Section 3.0.1 proposes a structure for the proton and the neutron. The predicted explanation of proton-neutron decay is given and a new class of particle is predicted.

Future directions are considered and conclusions are given in sections 4 and 5. A list of Nobel prizes to be awarded jointly for confirming the predictions made in this paper are given in Appendix A if the time displacement idea in Sinclair Pairs is correct.

2 Maxwell Spin Cups

Figure 2 illustrates a Maxwell Spin Cup. The spin cup comprises two gobbets of space time one displaced forwards in time and one displaced backwards in time (a Sinclair Pair), separated by some radial distance, each contains a magnetic potential. The gobbets of space time rotate around an axis in space. The force that holds the two regions of space together is termed a time like force and is a bit like Heisenberg’s uncertainty principle. It is beyond the scope of this paper to justify the existence of the time like force mathematically. This model gives rise to 8 distinct spin cups for the two possible senses of the magnetic fields and two directions of rotation. The magnitudes of the two magnetic potentials are assumed to be equal. It is beyond the scope of this paper to give a mathematical description of the distribution of potential created but it is very likely to have a dipole moment aligned with the spin axis and it is likely to be torroidal in nature.

Figure 1: A Maxwell Spin Cup with its Sinclair Pair. Rotating magnetic potentials hold the electrical potential in the vicinity of the cup away from zero. The two regions occupied by the magnetic potentials are displaced from each other in time and space. The fuchsia region is forward in time (displaced forward in time from the current time plane) and the blue region is displaced backwards in time.

There are eight possible configurations for a simple Maxwell Spin Cup. The magnetic field vectors [5] can be arranged [N-SS-N], [S-NN-S], [S-NS-N] and [N-SN-S] and the direction of rotation can be either clockwise or anti-clockwise. The eight possible Maxwell Spin Cups are illustrated in figure 2.

We introduce a compact naming convention for spin cups and label them according to the outside pole of the past dipole, the outside pole of the future dipole and the sense of the spin. An electron would then be a [NNu] or a [SSd] spin cup and a positron would be a [NNd] or a [SSd] spin cup. Neutrinos can be [NSu], [SNu], [SNd] or [NSd].

The 8 simple Maxwell Spin Cups

Figure 2: The 8 simple Maxwell Spin Cups for electron-spin-up, electron-spin-down, positron-spin-up, positron-spin-down and a bunch of neutrinos.

The spin up-ness and spin down-ness are governed by the pairings of the magnetic field vectors, either [N-SS-N] or [S-NN-S]. It is obvious that there is the possibility for spin up and spin down electrons to attract each other through rotating quadruple alignment if they share a common spin axis. As one has spin $1/2$ and the other spin $-1/2$ the combined pair will have spin 0. This predicted behaviour corresponds to the creation of Cooper pairs [1]. Neutrinos are made from leptons by changing the directions of a magnetic dipole. Which dipole is shifted forwards in time accounts for much of the unfathomable behaviour of neutrinos.

2.1 Creation of Maxwell Spin Cups

Figure 2.1 shows the electric and magnetic fields of a photon plotted along a time or space axis.

As a photon passes a General Relativistic [3] space-time gradient the wave form is distorted. The distortion will become unstable if the fields become multi-valued for a given portion of the photon.

The energy required in a photon for it to be capable of creating a electron-positron pair is 1.022 MeV in broad terms this corresponds to a wavelength of $1.213 \times 10^{-12}m$ This is going to be an upper bound on order of magnitude of the separation of the two electric field fragments and the temporal separation of the field fragments is going to be of the order of $1/4$ of $(1/\text{frequency})$ or about 10^{-20} seconds. The volume in which charge is confined will be smaller than the rotating radius of the *Sinclair Pair*. The quoted classical radius of an electron seems to be $< 2.817910^{-15}m$. The numbers don't appear to be catastrophically different given the length of the arms being waved.

The conditions for a photon shedding a pair of Maxwell Spin Cups is likely to be very specific. The time dilation across the photon will likely have to align portions of the magnetic field that are the same length. The phase of the photon at the alignment point must be such that there is some relation between the energy stored in the magnetic potential and in the electric potential (probably near equality).

Figure 3: Illustrative photon magnetic (blue) and electric (red) field strength along a time/space axis (black).

2.2 Quantising electric potential into apparent charge

This paper posits a new force created by displacing two regions of space off the current time plain. Heisenberg would have guessed that this force would be a function of the time displacement and the amount of energy involved. In order to create a displacement Newton would have argued you need to push backwards as well as forwards so the force required to create a displacement requires two ends. We call this new kind of force a *time like force*.

The force required to hold two rotating dipoles together (the *time like force* associated with their space and time displacement) must equal the centrifugal force associated with the rotating motion of the regions. It is thought that there are a very small number of stable solutions and this is the source of the quantisation of apparent charge and momentum.

The dipoles in the *Sinclair Pair* in the Maxwell Spin Cups for [NNu], [NNd], [SSu], [SSd] have the property that the wave function appears to be a duplicate of itself after 1/2 a rotation but they are not a direct duplicate until 1 full rotation, this may lead an observer to miss-read the angular momentum. I am just going to wave my arms in the air here and wait for a someone else to do the maths to prove this is the origin of spin 1/2 ness.

The author chooses to speculate that cosmic background radiation is evidence for the width of the stable zone of attraction as a chunk of electric potential and two magnetic dipoles subside into a stable state as an electron or positron is formed in a scattering event. The first spectral peak of cosmic background radiation is at a wavelength of about 2mm [6] or an energy of $6.53 \times 10^{-4} eV$ this compares to the mass of an electron of $0.511 \times 10^6 eV$. So you would guess that the mass of the electron is qunatised to probably better than 1 part in 10^{12} which agrees with experiment.

2.2.1 Neutrinos

Given that neutrinos have spin identical to electrons it is probable that you can get a neutrino from an electron by flipping one of the dipoles from N-S to S-N and visa versa. This is shown in figure 2.2.1. Neutrinos derived from electrons can have four states, the outer poles of the dipoles have to differ (so no electric potential is generated) and either the N pole out one is in the future (and the S pole out one is in the past) and these two cases can rotate clockwise or anti clockwise.

It is the presence of a chunk of magnetic field that allows a force to be applied to a region of space time. The act of separating two small chunks of space time in time acts to expand space

Figure 4: Illustrative effect of local time like drag on one side of a photon. Note the blue field line becoming non singular valued as it passes a location with large GR gradient.

time. Some time above the current time plain is pushed up slightly and time in the past of the current time plane is pushed backwards slightly by the expansion of time. It is this process that gives time it's arrow. Future time (and past time) is pushed away from us by the creations of neutrinos.

Neutrinos as we will see in the following section can form scattering pits in heavy particles. The sub-atomic scattering process is obviously not entirely charge based.

It seems likely that a neutrino is required in sub-atomic processes like neutron beta decay into a proton. The electromagnetic potential stored in the electron like spin cup in a neutron is transferred to another neutrino by flipping one dipole in each cup. The proposed creation mechanism for *Heisenberg struts* in sections 3.0.2 favours the motion of the pair of dipoles in a spin cup being entangled (or at least have a locked in distance measure between them in some way), relativity remains weird.

It is therefore possible to measure neutrino flux by measuring the half life of a free neutron. The proposed mechanism for neutron decay has the interesting property that half lives of elements may vary in different portions of the universe if the local neutrino density varies.

Neutrinos extend the time axis of space time (the small time shift they lock in pushes time apart). This offers the prospect of a faster than light drive that functions by removing the neutrinos from a region of space thus reducing the time between two points. Shovelling neutrinos from in front of you to behind you is a form of time travel.

Maxwell Spin Cup

Possible neutrino flavours from: e^-_{up}

Spin up-ness is conserved with a dipole flip.

Figure 5: Turning a [NNu] electron like Maxwell Spin Cup into neutrinos by flipping one of the dipoles in the Sinclair Pair. The can gives rise to a [SNU] or a [NSu] thing

3 Quarks

Quarks can be created in the fallout from high energy electron-positron collisions. Quarks have innate electrical potential and exist in tightly bound clusters of two or three quarks. The most surprising and interesting property of quarks is that the force between a pair of quarks rises with the distance they are apart (rather than falling off as $\frac{1}{r^2}$ like in some field potential process). The assertion that individual quarks have quantised charge of one of $(+2/3, -2/3, +1/3, -1/3)$ is experimentally derived but is not correct. The origin of the apparent charge results from the overlap of the electrically polarised zones of *Maxwell Spin Cups* in close proximity to each other rather than the existence of some fraction of an abstract quantity called charge.

For brevity we will only present the multiple Maxwell Spin Cup models for the four 3-quark (massive) particles: both kinds of proton, the neutron and a new particle we christen the *lyricon* (although this may just be a type 2 neutrino no longer capable of beta decay) after the spaceship designer in the Hitchhiker's Guide to the Galaxy.

The paper proposes a mechanism for how these particles are created and names the stretched portion of space time they contain (and capped by Maxwell Spin Cups) the *Heisenberg strut*. The paper argues that it is these locked stretchings of space time (the Heisenberg struts) that account for expansion and that the *lyricon* particle is a strong candidate model for dark matters. The mechanism by which they are created we call the *Hobson* mechanism and it accounts for how energy is created and held in the universe, it requires specific GR conditions to be met which are referred to as the *Hobson conditions for expansion* and it governs which particles can be created.

3.0.1 protons etc.

Figure 3.0.1 shows the two types of proton, they are: type 1 [$e^+ - e^- - e^+$] and type 2 [$e^+ - \nu - \nu$] where ν stands for neutrino. A type 1 proton can decay into a neutron by changing the orientation of the dipoles in one of its e^+ spin cups. Similarly a neutron can decay into a *type 2* proton by changing the orientation of the dipoles in its e^- spin cup. A type 2 proton can decay into a *lyricon* particle by flipping its remaining dipoles to be aligned with their spin axis. It is possible that the *lyricon* particle is in fact a type 2 neutron that is not capable of further decay and will have zero electric dipole moment. The Heisenberg struts remain intact giving you a model for dark matter particles.

3.0.2 Heisenberg Struts

A Heisenberg strut is a stretched portion of space time. It links two Sinclair Pairs where each pair is formed from dipoles from different locations and the bounce back from the relativistic creation event (meeting the *Hobson conditions*) leads to an internal tension and an external expansion of space time. Figure 3.0.2 illustrates the Hobson mechanism for creating Heisenberg struts.

It is likely that Spin Cups can trade dipoles in a strong relativistic gradient. This effectively separates the dipoles from a pair by an additional distance and this distance is space-time like. When the Spin Cups leave the relativistic gradient this new distance is locked in. Figure 3.0.2 shows how three Sinclair Pairs can trade dipoles and create 3 Heisenberg struts.

The formation of Heisenberg struts drives the expansion of the universe and creates the energy to go in it. Electrons and positrons are fused together to form protons and force apart space time in the process. If this model is correct stars create the hydrogen they burn as they create the space time they exist in. (they distance themselves from their neighbours in time through shedding clouds of neutrinos). The author does not pretend to fully understand Heisenberg struts. It may be that the Hobson conditions for GR torsion field fusion prohibit certain combinations of spin cups and type 1 protons never form.

The separation of the Maxwell Spin Cups containing the electron and positron has to some degree been estimated and a quoted value is approximately $10^{-15}m$, ball park estimation of the electric dipole moment is $1.60210^{-19} \times 10^{-15} = 1.60210^{-34} Cm$. This estimate is based on a point charge approximation, the value for a uniformly distributed charged shell will be a bit higher. This comes in well below the current upper limit determined experimentally of $310^{-26} Cm$ but is definitively non zero.

3.0.3 Heavier cousins

It seems very likely that the heavier versions of the electron, positron and neutrino result from a larger time displacement between the pairs of time displaced dipoles that make up the Sinclair Pair in the Maxwell spin cup. A common geometric form shared across different temporal shifts accounts for the analogous behaviour exhibited in particle families. If you have ever tried spinning a particularly fat American on an office chair you will understand why heavier particles are unstable.

4 Future Work

It remains to crunch the numbers to make sure *Maxwell Spin Cups* can stably exist and have a basin of attraction where if you nearly make one it will bleed off electrical potential and insure magnetic potential rotation matches the time like force that holds them together. The author wondered if there could exist a second type of *Maxwell Spin Cup* in which the *Sinclair Pair* contained an electric potential rather than the familiar magnetic one but there is likely a geometrical reason why this can't result in something stable.

Time displacement from the current time plane is also going to have to be studied and maths for the Heisenberg struts done. This pair of ideas has the potential to account for creation of energy and the expansion of space time in both space and time axes. These ideas point towards a constant inflation model for the evolution of the universe.

There needs to be an Pauli like exclusion mechanism where by spin cups refuse to occupy the same physical space. There is a list of joint Nobel prizes up for grabs in the appendix.

The central remaining question in Physics is: 'Is the time shifted chunk of magnetic dipole at the heart of the Sinclair Pair innately quantised or is the quantisation a result of a stable spin process'.

5 Conclusions

This paper posits a model for a mechanism by which electric potential can be localised and quantised. This shows charge does not exist so there may be nothing intrinsically special about its familiar quantisation. The existence of Cooper-pairs is a function of the the differing sense of the magnetic quadruple like polarisations associated with rotating [N-SS-N] and [S-NN-S] Maxwell Spin Cups. A mechanism is proposed for how scattering events create pairs of *Maxwell Spin Cups*. The paper explains the mechanics of spin 1/2 particles and predicts the existence of neutrinos. Neutrinos are held to contain two magnetic dipoles (shifted in time relative to each other) with their dipoles set so as not to create an electrical potential.

If you assume that the first peak in the cosmic microwave background is associate with the bleeding off of potential to allow a Maxwell Spin Cup to enter the stable state then the charge on the electron is quantised to one part in 10^{-12} .

This paper invents Heisenberg struts. This paper asserts that multi-quark particles arise when dipoles in multiple Maxwell Spin Cups (originating from differing spatial locations) are linked by Heisenberg struts.

The paper predicts that the neutron is comprised of a [electron - positron - neutrino] like set of Maxwell Spin Cups linked by Heisenberg struts and makes a ballpark prediction of its dipole moment and it is small but non zero and does not disagree with experimental determined values. It predicts there are two types of proton and a new dark matter particle called a *lyricon* (or possibly a type 2 neutron) which is three neutrinos held together by Heisenberg struts.

The paper offers a mechanism (the Hobson mechanism) that accounts for how energy is created as space time is expanded (and held open by Heisenberg struts). This paper predicts stars manufacture their own hydrogen as they create the space time round about themselves.

In reality (in physics) no additional dimensions are required only Maxwell's equations and General Relativity. The new idea is that you can create a force in space by displacing two regions of space time away form the current time plane. All of the quandaries about point charges are irrelevant, any theory that relies on the intrinsic quantisation of charge is no longer justifiable (because charge does not exist). It short, wave functions are fine, but charge as an abstract quantity does not exist.

6 Acknowledgements

The author acknowledges that the train of thought that lead to this paper started with a conversation at the Cambridge beer festival. I wanted a plausible space drive for a smutty scifi novel I was writing and things drifted to the subject of the Hobson GR Reaction mass less Torsion Drive (the Hobson Custard Drive) and how looking at quarks might provide a cheaper and less custardy alternative. You simply can't get away form the fact that the force between quarks is spring like and the only fundamental thing in physics that behaves like a spring is Heisenberg's

uncertainty principle and it involves time $\delta E \delta t = \lambda$. Bizarrely it was my 13 year old son who pointed out my initial neutrino model was wrong.

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A Appendix A: shared Nobel prizes up for grabs

The new physics presented in this paper makes predictions about how physics works. Physics without charge is different to the old physics. Physics with a model for the expansion of space time is different to the old physics. The data to verify the some of the new predicted behaviours may already exist in experimental observations.

The areas where join Nobel prizes will result form the new Physics in this paper include:

1. Demonstrate mathematically that the Maxwell Spin Cup is the correct model of electrons, positrons and neutrinos, confirm charge does not exist.
2. calculate the time displacement associated with a single neutrino and show that neutrino clouds account for the apparent presence of dark matter through dilating time round galaxies.
3. show that Heisenberg struts are the correct model for the structure in a proton or neutron.

4. show that the hydrogen in stars is produced by the Hobson GR torsion field reactor.
5. show that inflation is accounted for by neutrino and hydrogen production in stars.
6. create an experimental torsion field reactor in a particle accelerator. In principle this would create energy and hydrogen.
7. show nuclear decay is moderated by neutrinos and the local neutrino density determines half life and confirm there are two type of proton and two types of neutron, prove dipole flip is correct.
8. prove the cosmic background microwave spectrum is consistent with the shedding of photons as electric potential settles to its quantised value in a Maxwell Spin Cup.
9. show from data that certain properties of physics may vary in different regions of space if neutrino density varies.
10. determine whether it is the physical process of creating a Maxwell Spin cup that quantises the dipoles in it or whether space time is quantised.
11. show all the other particles that come out of particle accelerators are analogous to the normal ones we are made of. This may be worth more than one prize as it is quite time consuming.
12. rewrite atomic fusion models to account for how Heisenberg strut linked Maxwell Spin cups link up together.
13. there needs to be a Pauli exclusion principle for Sinclair Pairs.
14. design a practical Hobson torsion field reactor and use it for creating the hydrogen needed in terraforming.
15. spout endless drivel about a possible first star seed.
16. create pointless waffle about hydrogen creation in a black holes.
17. gull wealthy nutters into funding the neutrino sweep time-warping drive (it reduces the time between two points in space by sweeping away neutrinos leaving a time like tunnel in space time).
18. waffle pointlessly about what the 'entanglement' in a Heisenberg strut 'means'.
19. invent a multiply connected space time geometry where a star seed from the future is pushed far enough into the past for it to create the universe as we know it:) (and hope no one important notices, causality is not violated as long as space time is expanding).

Family of 3- Maxwell Spin Cup particles

Type 1 proton

Heisenberg struts carry the majority of the mass

neutron

type 2 proton

type 2 neutron
(predicted 'lyricon' particle does not decay)

The spin cups are bound together by Heisenberg struts..

Figure 6: Maxwell spin cups for the two kinds of proton, neutron and lyricon particles. The Heisenberg struts are locked in place by the dipoles in the spin cups. The spin cups are held together by the Heisenberg struts which push against time like repulsion.

Heisenberg strut formation.

General Relativistic compression of length scale and torsion field drag -> partner swap.

Dipoles from distinct locations now locked to wrong dipoles.

Space time has been stretched between A-a and between B-b and between C-c. This is the origin of the Heisenberg struts.

Figure 7: Heisenberg struts are created when spin cups from distinct locations trade dipoles in strong GR gradient region and then move out of the gradient regions, the resulting rebound of space time is a Heisenberg strut. It leaves a strong force between the pair of spin cups. Dipoles can be traded between multiple pairs of spin cups. A GR torsion field is created when 3 spin cups come together.